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THE INVOLVEMENT OF LAWYERS IN THE PROMOTION AND AWARENESS OF THE RIGHTS OF THE CHILD IN ROMANIA, AT THE PRE-UNIVERSITY AND UNIVERSITY LEVEL

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Summary. *In the whole of human rights, the rights of the child occupy an important place, recognized as such by school and justice. I propose that, through this work, I will analyze the way in which the lawyers in Romania understand how to get involved in the explanation, promotion and awareness of the rights of the child in Romania, as well as the age categories to whom this endeavor is addressed.*

As a scientific method for the elaboration of this paper, we used the observation method, the critical and comparative approach. As a result of my analysis, I intend to present rules that can constitute good practices regarding the promotion of children's rights and regarding the involvement of the lawyers' guild in prevention activities, not just assistance and representation in the defense of children's rights.

Keywords: *Human rights, best interests of the child, legal education, lawyer, the Child's Lawyer, project "Be a lawyer in your school" (FAST).*

Introductory aspects

Starting from the definitions of the Roman juriconsults, preserved to this day as guiding ideas, we see and understand law as an art - the art of good and equity, the art of living honorably, not harming another, giving everyone what is his. The Law of the XII Tables, in which the ancient Roman customary law was codified, regulated through provisions of public law and private law a series of legal institutions, such as: property regime, successions, family organization, the matter of obligations and a single contract, precisely like a real code. The law of the XII Tables was imprinted forever in the consciousness of the Roman people, being considered a symbol of its spirituality. Cicero claimed that the memorization of this law was a mandatory lesson for students, a "carmen necesarium".

And when we think about the future generations, we want each of our children, pupils and students to perfect this art, to preserve the principles of law and to adapt them skillfully to the society in which they live.

The issue of children's rights has been a challenge of all times, even if society, at one point, minimized the importance of these rights. Contemporary Romania, after December 1989, paid more attention to the rights of the child, nowadays becoming aware of the fact that it is very important that these rights are explained to the children in their own way.

In this sense, for the explanation of these rights and for the students to correctly understand the legal order and the rules of conduct in society, different categories of Romanian professionals in the field of law were involved, including lawyers.

1. Children's rights in Romanian legislation

1.1. Romanian legislation

When we think about human rights in general and children's rights in particular, we should imagine the chronological evolution of life and the importance of following some rules at the level of society and community, whatever they may be. And so we can start from the natural right and from the reason according to which childhood is the beginning segment of life, divided, in turn, into stages according to biological age.

Some historical sources that reach us from the medieval period show us the stages of childhood. Thus, we observe in the middle of the century. the 17th century, two such testimonies that claim that a " cocoon is the man from the moment he is born, until he is 4 years old. A child is called from four to fourteen years old" ("cocon iaste omul deaca naște, până la 4 ani. Copil se chiamă de la patru ani până la patrusprezece") [1], but also that a " cucon is called until the age of seven; young is called according to age, the male part is called from ten and a half to 14 years, and the female part from 9 and a half to 12 years" ("cucon să chiamă până al seaptele an de vîrstă; tînăr în măsură de vîrstă să cheamă parte bărbătească de la dzeace ai și giumătate până la 14 ai, iară parte fêmeiască de la 9 ai și giumătate până la 12 ai") [2] [3].

The rights of the child are responsibly regulated in Romanian legislation, starting with the fundamental law, the civil code and related laws, and in the regulation prior to the current Romanian civil code [4], these rights were also regulated in the former family code (which is repealed, currently). Next, we will present some of the legal provisions through which the Romanian legislator considered the regulation, promotion and protection of children's rights and which are included in the legal education programs carried out in schools.

The Romanian Constitution regulated the status of the child at the family level, in the relationship with his parents, and established that the situation of the child resulting from a marriage is identical to the situation of the child resulting from out of wedlock [5]. The provisions of the fundamental law were repeated exactly by the civil code in the content of art.260, called „children's equal rights”, as well as by Law no. 272/2004 on the protection and promotion of children's rights, in art.7 („The rights provided by this law are guaranteed to all children without any discrimination, regardless of race, color of skin, sex, language, religion, political opinion or other reson, nationality, ethnicity or social origin,

material situation, the rank and type of impairment, status at the moment of birth or acquired status, training and development or other difficulties of the child, parents or other legal representatives even any other distinction”).

In the context of the old family code [6], the Romanian legislator decreed that parental rights should be exercised only in the interest of the children, pursuing, in fact, the best interest of the child, which we will find regulated in detail, later, in the content Law no. 272/2004. Currently, the regulations regarding family relations and relations assimilated to these relations have been taken over and completed in the current civil code.

1.2. The best interest of the child promoted at school level

The idea of promoting children's rights and making children/students aware of their rights was capitalized in Romania after December 1989. Initially, the study of the Romanian Constitution was kept in the school curriculum, and then Civic Education and Social Education. added, courses that have a legal content and are usually taught by history professors. None of these subjects was taught by a professional in the field of law, as there was an incompatibility between the vast majority of practitioners in the legal field and the pre-university didactic activity.

Starting from 07.05.2021, by Law no. 184, regarding the amendment of art.16 of Law no. 51/1995 for the organization and exercise of the lawyer profession, the right of lawyers to be able to teach legal education in the pre-university environment was regulated. Practically, an incompatibility was raised for the lawyer profession, adding an supplement to art.16 lit.b), like as: „exercising the profession of lawyer is compatible with (...) didactic activities and functions in higher education, didactic activities with legal content in high school and gymnasium education”. [7]

The legal possibility to carry out didactic activities and hold positions in high school and gymnasium education also requires compliance with another mandatory condition in the Romanian education system, namely, the graduation by the lawyer-teacher of specialized studies called „psycho-pedagogical module” or studies master’s degree for the „pedagogy” specialization. If the lawyer teaches legal studies to middle school and high school students through voluntary (unpaid) activities, he is not required to have specialized studies in the field of psychopedagogy, for the moment.

I made the previous clarification to show the differentiation between the employment of the lawyer in a paid teaching activity, as a teacher, in contrast to the activity of the volunteer lawyer, which does not involve a consideration or remuneration of the respective lawyer.

These aspects do not imply a diminished attention to the best interest of the child, but, on the contrary, must be seen as a facility that the legislator makes to the

professional in the legal field, more precisely, the lawyer, to support him in the sense of promoting legal education in schools, paying attention to the best interest of the child.

2. The actors involved in the defense of children's rights

2.1. Family and school

Actions related to the promotion and defense of children's rights begin or should begin with family education. As a consequence, when we bring up the phrase „the seven years at home” we are also referring to the education that parents have the legal and moral obligation to give to each of their children. [8] The rights of the child appear, sometimes, even before the birth of the child, and this concept began since Roman antiquity and is still regulated today, in the Romanian legislation and in the legislation of other states.[9]

The problem arises when the parents themselves do not have the correct representation of some basic notions or have a distorted image of these rules and establish customs regarding family relations and/or the relations of their own family members with society. Another problem can arise if, although the parents know the rules of conduct, the rights and obligations of people quite well, they do not supervise their children and do not learn in time about the existence of cases of violation of these rules, ending up in the situation in which those children can become victims or aggressors.[10]

Therefore, each stage of development in a person's life has certain challenges, and the family has a very important role in the process of forming the future adult, as is known. In the family, the child receives the first advice about the rules of conduct and can learn about his rights and obligations. Once the child arrives in the education system, he comes into contact with other actors involved in child's education, namely teaching staff and non-teaching staff who complete, polish and perfect the child's knowledge, paying attention to the child's best interest. Among these knowledge are the rules of conduct, respectively, the rules of the class and the norms of the educational institution, which cannot in any way violate the rights of the child.

2.2. Authorities and public institutions with attributions in the defense of children's rights

We believe that it is impossible to talk about the promotion and protection of children's rights and their best interests without mentioning some aspects that refer to the notions of „public authority” and „public institution”. Apparently, the nine notions (authority and institution), if viewed in a broad sense, could be considered synonymous words. In reality, however, when we talk about each of these, we identify different meanings.

The difference between „public authority” and „public institution” can already be found in the definitions given to the two notions. Thus, we speak of

"public authority" when we refer to any state body or administrative-territorial units that act, under public authority, to satisfy a legitimate public interest; are assimilated to public authorities, for the purposes of this law, legal entities under private law that, according to the law, have acquired the status of public utility or are authorized to provide a public service, under the regime of public authority.[11]

„Public institution” is considered a legal entity of central, local or European public administration, which has personality and can manage public financial resources. In this context, we will make the previously mentioned differences.

Considering the above, we will differentiate between public authorities and public institutions because, when we talk about the promotion of children's rights, it is also done through the guild of lawyers or legal professionals, in general.

In the following we will list some of the two categories of public authorities and public institutions that have duties or object of activity to promote and protect the rights of the child or the best interest of the child and with which the legal profession is in direct relationship in various professional situations. Thus, in this context we mention: the Romanian Institute for Human Rights (RIHR), which is known as „an independent body with legal personality, established by Law no. 9/1991, which represents the first national institution for human rights created in Romania after 1989”. [12]

The National Authority for the Protection of Child Rights and Adoption (NAPCRA/ ANPDCA) is another guardian of the protection and promotion of children's rights. [13] This authority is represented at the local level by the public social assistance services (referred to by the acronym PSAS), which are organized at the level of municipalities and cities, as well as by the General Directorates for the Defense and Protection of Children's Rights (GDDPCR/DGASPC), organized at the level county, throughout the country. [14]

The National Council for Combating Discrimination (NCCD/CNCD) is „the autonomous state authority, under parliamentary control, which carries out its activity in the field of discrimination, guaranteeing the observance and application of the principle of non-discrimination, in accordance with domestic legislation. in force and with the international documents to which Romania is a party”. [15]

The People's Advocate (PA/AVP) - The Children's Advocate

The People's Advocate institution is an autonomous public authority and independent of any other public authority and aims to defend the rights and freedoms of natural persons in relations with public authorities.

„Considering the fact that the basic activity is the resolution of citizens' petitions, the institution of the People's Advocate receives and distributes the

requests submitted by the persons injured by the violation of the rights and freedoms of citizens by the public administration authorities and decides on these requests; pursues the legal resolution of the requests received and requests the authorities or officials of the public administration in question to stop violating the rights and freedoms of citizens, to restore the rights of the petitioner and to repair the damages.” [16]

Moreover, if we think that „in serving the best interests of children, we serve the most important interests of humanity” (according to the American politician Carol Bellamy), we can find another justification for why, alongside the institution of the People’s Advocate, a structure was established in the subordination of this institution, called „the Child Advocate”.

Important to remember is the opinion according to which „the appearance of the Children’s Advocate, as an autonomous public authority, determined not only the simple invocation of a set of universally valid standards and obligations regarding the rights of the child, but also the elaboration and adoption of modern legislation, which effectively defends the rights of the child in Romania and to ensure their implementation in accordance with the provisions of the UN Convention adopted by the General Assembly of the United Nations on November 29, 1989”. [17]

Courts of law

At the level of the judicial system, there are specialized courts to judge cases involving minors and family. In the vast majority of cases, specialized jurisdiction is exercised within some sections of the courts. In Romania, we encounter an exceptional situation in Brașov, where there is a specialized court for minors and family.[18]

And because the idea we wanted to bring to attention through our study refers to the involvement of lawyers in the promotion and protection of children’s rights, as well as in relation to legal education in school, we will further present what, in concrete terms, this activity consists of lawyers.

3. The activity carried out by the legal professions in favor of the defense of children's rights

3.1. Categories of legal professionals who contribute to the defense of children’s rights

Through their professional training, graduates in legal sciences defend human rights. Each of them exercises their profession according to the specifics of the chosen field and in which they work. In relation to the theme of this study, we have listed the legal professions, but also the limits between which these professionals encounter human rights and children’s rights, respectively:

The lawyer, who pleads in cases involving minors or minors and family cases (denial of paternity, divorce, establishment of a minor visitation schedule,

establishment of residence of the child, alimony, abandonment of the family, custody of the child, order of protection, appointment of a guardian for the conclusion of a legal act in which the child is one of the contracting parties).

The legal advisor, the specialist inspector from an institution that (also) deals with the protection of children's rights or *the probation advisor* (the latter having different powers), can intervene as representatives of one of the authorities that have powers in the defense of children's rights.

The judge, as a professional of the law that we meet in the disputes of minors and the family when the question of law reaches the court, to be resolved by court decision.

The prosecutor and the police officer, when there is a criminal case, which involves the defense of a social value specific to criminal law (offences related to family life or which presumes the involvement of a child as a victim or suspect/offender).

The public notary, especially after the entry into force of the current Romanian civil code, when we talk about divorce by notarial convention or the power of attorney/mandate that one of the parents gives to the other parent or both parents give it to a third person because that person accompanies the minor outside borders of Romania or to be able to request a passport that includes the data of the minor child or in the case of a succession debate that also presumes the involvement of a minor child.

The bailiff, who can intervene at the time of execution of a court decision establishing certain rights in favor of a child, rights that are not executed voluntarily, without the intervention of coercive force.

The previously mentioned examples, for each of the legal professions, are not limiting, but simply exemplary, to highlight the category of legal activities in which each of the legal professionals in Romania can be involved.

Returning to the profession of lawyer in relation to children's rights, the lawyer contributes, on the one hand, to the protection of these rights, and on the other hand, he can promote them and carry out activities aimed at preventing the violation of children's rights.

3.2. Lawyers in the promotion and awareness of children's rights

Lawyers had several opportunities to get involved in the promotion and awareness of children's rights. Of these occasions, I remember you only a few, which were promoted more, respectively: activities in school classes (usually management classes, in secondary education), the organization of simulated and simplified trials, having as their theme various stories collected from the school curriculum, the activity organized by the Association for Dialogue and Solidarity of Lawyers, the National Union of Romanian Bar Associations in partnership with the Ministry of National Education.

Children's rights were also promoted by other non-governmental organizations, in partnership with the school inspectorates and/or directly with different schools, such as the older situation of the VeDem Just Association, which promoted legal education in schools in Romania and the Republic of Moldova (years 2019-2020) or a more recent example of the Association „The imprint of Good” („Amprenta de Bine”, 2021-2022), in the schools of Constanța county, Romania.

Also, among the non-governmental organizations that were directly involved in protecting and promoting children's rights, we mention the „Save the Children” Foundation. As a primary concern, this foundation had in view the field of education, including legal education.

In promoting and raising awareness of children's rights, in 2022 a partnership was established between the National Union of Romanian Bar Associations (through the counties bar associations) and the Ministry of National Education (through the county school inspectorates). The project was called „Be a lawyer in your school”, bearing the romanian acronym „FAST” („Fii avocat în școala ta”). Initially, a pilot project was carried out, comprising five modules, between March and June of 2022. Later, following the interest shown by other schools, as well as the change in the structure of the school year, the project was structured on four modules, the concentration of information thus so that it can be transmitted on time, in the first semester, to the students.

The second stage of this project took place between November and December 2022 and enjoyed the same success as the first stage. The project pursued the same ideas, shared with pre-university students.

The novelty with which it began in the second stage consisted in the fact that the addressability area was extended to high school students, starting from the 5th grade. We specify that in the first stage, which took place at the end of the last school year (as I mentioned before), only the 7th grades and the first three high school grades were included, the 8th and 12th grades being excluded, who were to take exams at the end of the year (National Assessment, respectively the baccalaureate exam).

Lawyers who taught legal education courses in schools spoke to the students about the three powers of the state, the Romanian Constitution, the Romanian judicial system, the rules according to which the legal norm is applied [19], children's rights and obligations, about how children and/or their families can be held accountable for the illegal acts of those children. Topics specific to the age segment specific to the school period and the challenges that students may face were addressed, in particular: the phenomenon of bullying [20], crimes [21] and computer crime, contact with prohibited substances, acts that affect life , the

bodily integrity and intimate life of children, the legal conditions in which children can obtain income from work. At the same time, role-playing games were used, not just theoretical presentations.[22] Moreover, the project coordinators from the National Union of Bars of Romania made and developed summaries and materials in the Power Point system, which made legal education classes attractive for students and easy to teach by lawyers.

We specify that these courses were addressed to students from the pre-university environment, respectively, gymnasium and high school.

Regarding the university environment, we note that there are bachelor's and master's programs that have included courses in the legal field, but these do not always consider children's rights or human rights. The courses we refer to complement the specializations of the study programs in which the students are preparing.

Conclusions

At the end of our study, we can draw some conclusions regarding the involvement of the body of Romanian lawyers in the promotion and awareness of children's rights. These conclusions take into account, first of all, the quality of those who chose to get involved in the promotion of these rights. Specifically, lawyers, legal professionals who have professional experience, willingness to volunteer, and public speaking skills, can help successfully present and explain these rights.

Second, when the target audience for these courses is, as I mentioned earlier, only middle school and high school students. For them, essential information regarding the rights of the child, as well as the child's relationship with adults, were taken into account.

Regarding the university environment, we believe that the notions conveyed to students cannot change the university curriculum to bring specific information about children's rights into the education plans. We also believe that legal concepts that may be necessary and useful to undergraduate and graduate students must complement the professional training of these students, which goes beyond the ability to analyze the specific rights and obligations of children.

Legal notions in the field of promoting human rights, in general, and children's rights, in particular, are part of the university programs of law faculties and may be part of the programs of other study programs that require knowledge of this information.

Third, as a lawyer, teacher, and parent, I believe that this approach of law enforcement in partnership with teachers is welcome, a model of good practice, and produces effects worthy of consideration.

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